

USING THE ART OF NAMING TO CREATE ERGONIMS

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It is clear to everyone that the vitality, changeability, and development of nature and society in a dialectical relationship depends on the regular repetition of events and phenomena in a certain space and time. In this process, language emerges as the most important bolt that drives society. "Language has so many and unique properties that it contains not one, but several structures. The divine trinity in language: language ↔ culture ↔ human personality incarnate. All the power of the language is related to the fact that it is created and enriched in the language of the people and in the process of work. When people do a lot of work, they feel the need to communicate with each other through words.

Language is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that expresses the unique national-cultural characteristics of peoples. Its characteristic image, norm, symbol, etc. are not found in any other system. Language objectively reflects people's worldview and culture. It is precisely because of this feature that each national language presents its own unique linguistic landscape of the world and is passed down from generation to generation in the form of forms of communication and language traditions¹. Language reflects geography, history, climate, living conditions of people². It is precisely this process that underlies the immortality of language. When a nation stops thinking, becomes mute, its language begins to decline. On the contrary, the language of creative, innovative peoples will continue to develop. We can see this in the example of the Uzbek language.

The opening of Uzbekistan to the world due to independence completely changed the thinking, outlook and hopes of the Uzbek nation. Industry, production, finance and credit, banking, diplomacy, household life and other fields have entered the news and innovative ideas recognized by the world community in one form or another. In our country, world-class enterprises, organizations, and institutions related to industry, automobile manufacturing, agriculture, medicine, education, and management have been established. A significant number of them were created in cooperation with other countries and are currently operating as joint ventures. They produce various products that fully meet the requirements of the world market and are successfully sold in the domestic and foreign markets. This, in turn, leads to the emergence of new words, terms, terms and ergonims in all areas of the Uzbek language.

It is known that ergonims are considered one of the smallest micro-scopes included in the onomastic scope. Their emergence and development in our language goes back to the processes of emergence and development of new methods in name selection and naming

¹ Телия В.Н. Русская фразеология. Семантический, прагматический и лингвокультурологические аспекты. – М.: Школа «Языки русской культуры», 1996. – С. 231. 288 с.

² Тер-Минасова С.Г. Язык и межкультурная коммуникация. – М.: Слово, 2000. – С. 38. 264 с.

principles. The "spreading of wings" of ergonomics in society is largely due to the globalization of production, the acquisition of a conglomerate character, full transition to the market economy, advertising and sales of the created product. This in itself is onomastics, which is considered a department that studies the laws of appearance and change of popular nouns in the advanced languages of the world at the beginning of the 21st century. (юн. *onomastike – the art of naming*) is explained by the rapid transition to a new quality stage - the naming stage, which meets the requirements of the time in all respects and can fully satisfy the demands of consumers.

Нейминг the word is English *naming* – *номлаш* is taken from the word and includes complex processes related to product naming, brand creation, and service provision. Naming is also called *semonemics*³. Abroad, this service has grown to a professional level, some names have become brands, that is, well-known names known all over the world. To this **LOGO** (*In Danish leg godt, ie “яхши ўйна” means*); **IBM** (*International Business Machines (Biznes uchun xalqaro mashina) derived from the abbreviation*); **Samsung** (*in Korean “3 ta yulduz” gives meaning*) we can take brands as an example.

The legal basis of the matter was created by the head of our state in order to continue the ancient traditions and increase the prestige of the mother tongue in our country and in the international arena. Decree No. PF 6084 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 21, 2020 "On measures to further develop the Uzbek language in our country and improve the language policy" was one of the comprehensive works implemented in this way⁴.

The greatest danger in the decline of languages is the growing neglect of their own language, the formation of feelings of indifference and the spread of this to others. In the region where such a mood prevails, the range of movement of the national language in practice will be narrowed, language rules will be violated, and confusion will arise in the use of words. We can clearly see this today in the example of the Uzbek language. In the names of organizations and enterprises, titles, and slogans, we encounter cases of indifference and indifference, as above. Examples of this are the names of enterprises, organizations and institutions in the city of Tashkent. For example, let's pay attention to some names given to hotels, medical institutions, trade enterprises. There are now thousands of such names. It must be admitted that among them there are also names based on our national values, geographical location of the place, and the opinion of the population is taken into account: *LABZAK, BEK, SAMIR, DUNYO, SOY, AFSONA, ATLAS, OPOM, ORZU, XADRA, SAYYOH, SALTANAT, OQSHOM, SARBON* (hotel names), *Davo, Ozon, Navbahor, Dori-darmon* (pharmacy names), *Bekajon, Visol, Zilola* (store names) and such names include. But, unfortunately, 90% of the names given are in English, Russian or mixed languages and do not meet the state language requirements at all.

However, in Article 20 of the Law "On State Language": "Signs, announcements, price lists and other visual and verbal informational texts are issued and published in the state language and may be translated into other languages";

Article 22: "The names of geographical objects are reflected in the state language", it is written clearly⁵.

³ <https://www.marketch.ru>.

⁴ Мамлакатимизда ўзбек тилини янада ривожлантириш ва тил сиёсатини такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги ПФ 6084-сонли Фармон//“Xalq so‘zi” newspaper, 2020/21/10, Number: 221-222. P.:1-9.

⁵ lex.uz

In practice, the articles of the Law "On the State Language" are grossly violated. Such names can be divided into the following groups:

1. Names of Uzbek words misspelled according to Russian pronunciation: *HILAL, SULTAN, AKSAROY, TAJ MAHAL, CHINARA* (hotel, restaurant names), *Asel, Amilla, Oxu med* (pharmacy names) etc.

Among these names is TAMURLAN, which once served to condemn the person of Amir Temur, whom we praise today (Tashkent city, Minglar street, 39) name is also found. In addition to the name of the hotel, transport and travel companies *Tamerlan tour, Tamerlan Estate, Tamerlan travel* You will be amazed at how formal it looks. Such silly names are nothing but disrespect not only for the state language, but also for our history and our great ancestors. It should be said that it was formed on the basis of the names of our great ancestors Navoiy imzo, Glinka dental, Names like Babur last can neither meet our national values nor the spelling rules of the Uzbek language?!

2. Arabic *al-* nouns formed with the article: *AL AMIN, AL-HOSILOT* etc. City streets, to relevant institutions *Ал-Хоразмий, Ал-Фаробий, Ал-Бухорий, Putting names such as al-Farghani fits the language criteria, but the above and "ал-Воҳид шифо"* (Tashkent city, Shaikhontohur district, Karasaroy street, 1), *"ал-Хаким трукотаж"* (Andijan region, Khojaabad district, Usta Hakim Uraimov street, 1), *al-Nur* (Tashkent city, Sergeli district, 6th sub-district) I did not know which rules of the Uzbek language correspond to putting names like?

3. Names in the form of a combination of words that express abstract concepts: *ZILOL BAXT* (hotel name), *Davron Nur, Xizr savdo* (magazine names), *Safo Tibbiyot* (hospital name) etc

4. Names made using English+Uzbek words or vice versa: *GRAND UZBEGIM, THE ROYAL MEZBON, ICHAN QALA VILLAS, MEROS BOUTIQUE HOTEL, RAKAT PLAZA, ART RAKAT, XON PALASE, SHOSH PALASE, BO'STON HOTEL, SHARQ HOTEL, QUSHBEGI PLAZA, GRAND TASHKENT, AYVON EKSPRESS, DOPPI HOSTEL, ISO HOSTEL, GRAND JAHON, GRAND NUR, GRAND FAROBIY* (hotel name), *Sayt Optima, Vitamed Medical, Parents Holiday, Cardio life, City Med* (hospital name), *Osiyo Farm, Shoh-farm, Mubina pharm, Nemur farm, javoxir Farm, Фарм-Феруза, Rishad Med, Hadra group* (pharmacy names), *Brandbox Film Tashkent, Ilkhom Cinema Klub* (the name of the cinema). The English words included in such names have not yet been fully assimilated into the Uzbek language, perhaps they will never be assimilated... Creating such a name leads to extreme artificiality, to condense the words of our mother tongue, get rid of it.

ANVAR'S CUETS (hotel name), *Rustam's shop, M MAKON* (shop name) the same can be said about names like

5. Mixed nouns: *GRAND SOHIL HOTEL, COMFORD UZ HOTEL, MIRZO BOUTIQUE HOTEL, HAPPY HOUSE HOTEL TASHKENT* (hotel name), *Hayat Medikal centre, Manado-amon shifo, Zilola medikal centre* (hospital name), *Apteka Euro Apteka, Karavan Farm Shifo, Nur-nazar biznes, Madina bonu farm savdo, аптека Халил Ота, Doniyor Farm-m, Farm Invest Dil* (pharmacy names). It is time to put an end to such names.

6. Names from English roots: *HILTON, PAMADA, STAR, SILVER* (hotel name), *Evos, Posado, Bravo* (the name of the cinema). Such one-word names may be foreign brands, but when there are beautiful and unique words in the Uzbek language, naming these capitals in

such a way without having any connection to foreign countries is nothing more than an extreme ignorance in choosing a name.

7. Names with both bases derived from foreign words: *LEADER HOTEL, BAVARIA PLAZA, ART HOTEL, DANIEL GARDEN, SILK ROAD, MAYA TOUR, DREAM HOUZE, ORIENT STAR* (hotel name), *Medilife farma, Cardio Farm, Fly Farm, Nika Pharm, Well pharm, Best pharm, Ventus Pharm, karvak Farm, City Pharm, Eko pharma, Bravo pharma, Antex plus, Herb-Med* such as (pharmacy names). If you pay attention, it becomes clear that such names are also given in imitation of foreign countries.

8. Names made of three or more foreign words: *GRAND MIR HOTEL, KIM SAT GAT, ART APART HOTEL, GRAND ART HOTEL, OREON INN HOTEL, ASTER HOTEL GROUP, HOTEL AZIA WAY, LE GRANDE PLAZA* (hotel name), *Vita Stimul Med, Avisa Med Servis, Cardio star plus, Mir Pharma Optikal, Медикал саре севуце* (hospital name), *Apteka EkoMed, Elit Pharm Organik, Аптека капсула плюс, Аптека Euro Аптека* (pharmacy names) etc. These names also show disrespect and disregard for the state language.

9. Numbers, names mixed with various graphic symbols: *Brand 910, Silk & Wine 96* (hotel name), *Neurofax-B* (hospital name), *A5, Apteka -03, 36,6,333, A5 HUMO, Аптека 7777, 999, Oxy med N' 59/1* (pharmacy names), *5d Cinema, 7d Cinema, 7d – kinotetr* (movie theater names) etc. Such names also came from abroad. It is time to review them as well.

10. Names based on Russian words and phrases: *Голубые купола, Гостница Хасият Абдувахоб, гостница Тройка, У бабушки, Izumrudniy* (hospital name), *Уголок, Эмиля, Ягодка, Поплавок, Курица-гриль* (the name of the places to eat), *+5 Пятёрочка* Such names do not correspond to our national mentality or state language policy. It is possible to Uzbekize them and replace them with alternatives.

11. Texts in Turkish, German, French, Chinese: *Giz Galasi, Zuleyha, Gunesh, Sherbet, Guten, Инь-Ян* as. Upon investigation, it turns out that these names have nothing to do with the above languages. Therefore, it is necessary to refrain from calling the names of places with the correct word. Attempting to create new words such as *Gozalina, Asilzadakhon, Artchehra* under the influence of a foreign language leads to the narrowing and impoverishment of the language.

If we pay attention in time and do not prevent it, artificial names like the above will crawl on our tongue like weeds and will surround it from all sides in the coming years. We can prove our point with the example of the word "cinema" and "market". Place names include *Next Cinema, Royal Cinema, Vega Cinema, Mega Cinema, Grand Cinema, Drive Cinema, Grand Cinema, Premier Cinema, Cinema Bollywood*. They are names that are forced into our speech and contradict the above-mentioned articles of the state language in every way.

The word "market" has already covered our language. Its scope has reached such a level that this word is actively used in all forms of naming patterns. For example: a) uzbek name+market: *Ali market, A'lo market, Baraka market, Do'stlik market, Fayoz market, Saroy market, Saodat market* etc. б) russian name-market: *Samara market, Ekomarket, Moy market* etc. в) english word-market: *City market, Market foods, Good market, Cinema market* etc. г) *Market 18, S-market, Zqr market, S-klass* etc.

In conclusion, the Uzbek language is one of the oldest languages in the world with the richest and deepest historical roots. The Uzbek language, as the state language, must be clean and pure like the sacred and miraculous springs of our country, and always suitable for consumption. Its internal and external possibilities are endless and unparalleled. To use it

appropriately, to fight for the purity and naturalness of the language, to fully comply with the standards of the state language every moment, every second, to demand the same from others, to preserve the purity and freshness of the mother tongue, the motherland that washed us all, raised us white, brought us to adulthood, It is our honorable and at the same time sacred duty to our MOTHER TONGUE.

After all, as President Shavkat Mirziyoev said in his greeting to the people of Uzbekistan on the occasion of the "Uzbek Language Day":

“Language is a great force that elevates the spirit of the nation. Love and loyalty to the motherland begins with love and loyalty to the mother tongue⁶”.

⁶ “Xalq so‘zi” newspaper, 2020/21/10. Number: 221-222, P:1.

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